

Cardiac pathophysiology: exploring online education trends among iranian students

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Investigación sobre la educación en línea entre estudiantes iraníes de optometría

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Abstract

Undoubtedly, online education has emerged as a prominent and effective approach, particularly in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic, for students. On one hand, this method has evolved significantly owing to the rapid advancements in communication technologies. On the other hand, it has become indispensable due to the Covid-19 pandemic and the necessity to suspend traditional in-person education. It has proven to be one of the most impactful methodologies within the realm of academic education. In this study, we aim to delve into the field of cardiac pathophysiology, exploring the intricate workings of the heart and its physiological processes. Cardiac pathophysiology is a branch of medicine that delves into the deviations from normal heart function and structure, seeking to comprehend the underlying mechanisms of various cardiac disorders. This descriptive-analytic research focuses on a cohort of 112 undergraduate, postgraduate, and PhD students in Iran. A meticulously crafted questionnaire was employed to assess their experiences and perceptions of online courses and their educational objectives. We conducted a comprehensive analysis of student demographics based on

various criteria, and the outcomes of online education were compared across different educational levels. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software to derive meaningful insights. The study findings revealed that a majority of students across all three academic levels expressed satisfaction with over 60% of their online courses. Interestingly, as the academic level increased, student satisfaction also demonstrated an upward trend. Notably, 50.9% of the participants indicated a desire to continue with online classes even after the conclusion of the Covid-19 pandemic. This underscores the effectiveness and acceptance of online education. However, it is essential to acknowledge that online education is not without its challenges. Issues such as slow internet connections and limited interactions with instructors can be perceived as drawbacks of this method. Despite these challenges, the overall consensus among students suggests that online education has been a valuable and satisfactory mode of learning for them.

Keywords: Cardiac Pathophysiology, Covid-19 pandemic, Online education, Student satisfaction, Technology advancements

Sin lugar a dudas, la educación en línea se ha convertido en un enfoque destacado y eficaz para los estudiantes, particularmente en el contexto de la pandemia de Covid-19. Por un lado, este método ha evolucionado significativamente debido a los rápidos avances en las tecnologías de la comunicación. Por otro lado, se ha vuelto indispensable debido a la pandemia de Covid-19 y la necesidad de suspender la educación tradicional presencial. Ha demostrado ser una de las metodologías de mayor impacto dentro del ámbito de la educación académica. En este estudio pretendemos profundizar en el campo de la fisiopatología cardíaca, explorando el intrincado funcionamiento del corazón y sus procesos fisiológicos. La fisiopatología cardíaca es una rama de la medicina que profundiza en las desviaciones de la función y estructura normal del corazón, buscando comprender los mecanismos subyacentes de diversos trastornos cardíacos. Esta investigación descriptiva-analítica se centra en una cohorte de 112 estudiantes de pregrado, posgrado y doctorado en Irán. Se empleó un cuestionario meticulosamente elaborado para evaluar sus experiencias y percepciones sobre los cursos en línea y sus objetivos educativos. Realizamos un análisis exhaustivo de la demografía de los estudiantes basado en varios criterios y se compararon los resultados de la educación en línea en diferentes niveles educativos. El análisis estadístico se realizó utilizando el software SPSS para obtener información significativa. Los hallazgos del estudio revelaron que la mayoría de los estudiantes de los tres niveles académicos expresaron satisfacción con más del 60% de sus cursos en línea. Curiosamente, a medida que aumentó el nivel académico, la satisfacción de los estudiantes también demostró una tendencia ascendente. En particular, el 50,9% de los participantes indicó su deseo de continuar con las clases en línea incluso después de la conclusión de la pandemia de Covid-19. Esto subraya la eficacia y aceptación de la educación en línea. Sin embargo, es esencial reconocer que la educación en línea no está exenta de desafíos. Problemas como conexiones lentas a Internet y interacciones limitadas con los instructores pueden percibirse como inconvenientes de este método. A pesar de estos desafíos, el consenso general entre los estudiantes sugiere que la educación en línea ha sido un modo de aprendizaje valioso y satisfactorio para ellos.

Palabras clave: Fisiopatología cardíaca, Pandemia de Covid-19, Educación en línea, Satisfacción de los estudiantes, Avances tecnológicos

In late 2019, the coronavirus outbreak began in the city of Wuhan, Hubei province, China. Subsequently, the causative agent was identified as the SARS-CoV-2 virus, leading to a global outbreak of COVID-19, which was officially declared a global pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO) in March 2020. Following this declaration, numerous nations, including Iran, implemented measures to control the spread of the epidemic by isolating infected individuals and tracing contacts¹⁻⁵. This included the implementation of curfews and the suspension of in-person education at Iranian universities. In response, the Ministry of Health introduced distance education as a means of continuing educational activities. Consequently, virtual education became a prevalent mode of instruction in medical universities.

Distance education, in the context of cardiac pathophysiology, refers to the use of computer technology to deliver educational content online or offline⁵⁻⁸. This approach encompasses various forms of digital learning, including computer-based training, Internet-based training, virtual classrooms, and digital collaboration. Despite the significance of these online educational methods, there is limited published evidence regarding the evaluation of their effectiveness in teaching cardiac pathophysiology. However, certain global events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, have had profound consequences and implications, including the transformation of education systems⁹⁻¹². As the pandemic spread globally, educational institutions worldwide decided to discontinue in-person classes to mitigate the transmission of the disease. Many educators, instead of canceling their courses, transitioned to providing content and assessing learning outcomes through distance learning and online education.

This shift to online education, which occurred abruptly in the middle of the semester, prompted educators and curriculum designers to make considerable efforts to ensure a smooth transition¹³⁻¹⁶. Although the urgency of the situation did not appear to lead to a decline in educational standards or changes in learning outcomes, there is a paucity of comprehensive studies in this area. The available research indicates that virtual education in the field of cardiac pathophysiology can be successful and efficient when educational content is thoughtfully designed and rigorously evaluated^{17,18}.

Reviewing the existing literature, many studies focus on demonstrating the effectiveness of online courses in the context of cardiac pathophysiology^{6,12}. Some studies have introduced educational software applications, particularly in the field of online medicine and dentistry education, which can be beneficial for graduates in the healthcare sector^{7,19,20}.

In Iran, the education of cardiac pathophysiology is structured into three levels, typically spanning several years of undergraduate, master's, and doctoral studies⁶. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, most classes were conducted in traditional face-to-face settings. However, with the onset of the pandemic, virtual training methods were introduced. At Shahid Beheshti University of Medical Sciences, various platforms such as Adobe Connect, ZOOM, and a native Iranian platform named Navid were utilized for virtual education in the field of cardiac pathophysiology.

Given the far-reaching impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on a global scale, it is anticipated that this crisis will continue to significantly affect education for an extended period. Consequently, this study was conducted to identify students' preferences and experiences during the period of remote learning, with the aim of actively involving students in the development of distance learning methods. This approach seeks to achieve the most satisfying and reliable educational outcomes while balancing students' preferences with the quality of instruction in the domain of cardiac pathophysiology.

This study is a descriptive-analytical investigation focusing on the pathophysiology of the heart. The study population included 112 students from Shahid Beheshti University of Medical Sciences, encompassing three academic levels: undergraduate, master's, and doctoral, all of whom were engaged in online classes. The sampling method employed in this research was a census approach, encompassing all students from the three academic levels participating in online courses. Participants remained in the study throughout, with exclusions only occurring in cases where students withdrew from the course. The research instrument utilized was an online questionnaire hosted on the Google Form platform, which students completed during the semester through provided links. The questionnaire designed by the researcher consisted of two primary sections: Demographic Information: This section included questions about age, gender, semester, and educational level. Multiple-Choice Survey Questions: This part contained inquiries related to the students' experience with online classes before the Covid-19 pandemic, the time interval between the commencement of online classes, the frequency of online classes per week, the duration of online class sessions, the tools used to participate in online classes, the type of online classes attended, the frequency of platforms used, the type of recorded classes, the frequency of participation in online classes, the level of difficulty experienced in online class participation, the reasons

for non-participation, methods of communication with professors, communication with professors during recorded classes, students' perceptions of the advantages and disadvantages of online education, suggestions for improving online education, overall satisfaction with online education, participation frequency in online webinars, satisfaction with online webinars, selection of the type of student class, and students' desire to engage in online classes.

In the current study, 112 participants were enrolled, with an average age of 23.6 ± 6.2 years, spanning from 19 to 58 years. Of the participants, 57.1% were female, and the remaining 42.9% were male. Among the participants, 81.3% were pursuing undergraduate studies, 12.5% were enrolled in master's programs, and 6.3% were pursuing specialized PhD programs. Table 1 displays the demographic characteristics of the participants under investigation in the context of cardiac pathophysiology.

EDUCATIONAL DEGREE	TOTAL	MALE	FEMALE	SEMESTER				
				1	3	4	5	7
BSc	91	37	54	39	20	0	13	19
MSc	14	6	8	8	6	0	0	0
Ph.D.	7	5	2	0	2	3	2	0
TOTAL	112	48	64	47	28	3	15	19

According to the findings of this survey, let's discuss the pathophysiology of the heart. Prior to the Covid-19 epidemic, 8.8 percent of undergraduate students had taken online courses, compared to 14.3 percent of postgraduate students and 42.9 percent of PhD students. The interval between the start of online classes after the onset of the social constraints associated with the Covid-19 pandemic was more than 30 days (71.4%), 30 days for 16.1%, and less than 30 days for the rest. Most online classes were held 3 times a week (48.2%) and then 4 times a week (16.1%). Moreover, most online classes were held during 8-14 (82.1%). The majority of online classes for undergraduate students are 3 times a week, which was less than 3 times a week for other students.

Table 2 shows how student in all grades satisfied from different communication platforms and distribution of their used platforms.

In the context of cardiac pathophysiology, the following observations were made. The primary advantage identified by cardiology students in online classes was

the reduced risk of physical interaction, with 82.7% of them favoring this aspect. Conversely, only 1.8% of students found ease of attendance to be an advantage. On the downside, the majority of students, approximately 90.1%, considered online classes to have a negative impact on their learning abilities. In contrast, the least disadvantage reported was the inaccessibility to a quiet place, affecting only 0.9% of students (Table 3). The study also indicated that more than 92% of students utilized Adobe Connect for their online learning needs. Additionally, nearly 35% of students expressed a satisfaction level of 60% or higher regarding their online learning

experiences. Furthermore, it was revealed that nearly 50% of students expressed a preference for a blended learning approach, combining both online and in-person methods (Table 3 and 4). It is suggested that incorporating face-to-face learning alongside online methods may enhance students' satisfaction and improve their learning abilities in the field of cardiac pathophysiology.

Students often use smartphones to attend online classes (74.1%) (Figure 1). Most undergraduate students use laptops (79.3%) for attending online classes.

Table 2. Communication platform and students' percentage of the satisfaction of online learning according to students' grades

Grade	Communication platform		Satisfaction			
	ADOBE CONNECT	SKYPE	<30%	30 to <60%	60-90%	>90%
BSC(n=91)	100.0%	0.0%	30.8%	42.9%	26.4%	0.0%
Msc(n=14)	71.4%	28.6%	0.0%	7.1%	50.0%	42.9%
Phd(n=7)	42.9%	57.1%	0.0%	0.0%	85.7%	14.3%
Total (n=112) mean	92.9%	58.2%	25.0%	35.7%	33.0%	6.3%

Table 3. Advantages and disadvantages of online learning according to students' grades

Grade	Advantages					Disadvantages				
	LRPC*	Lower Cost	Easy to learning	Ease of Attendance	Other	NSD**	LCT***	Poor learning	Inaccessibility to a quiet place	Other
BSC(n=91)	80.9%	52.8%	11.2%	0.0%	5.6%	43.3%	52.2%	94.4%	1.1%	8.9%
Msc(n=14)	85.7%	71.4%	28.6%	7.1%	0.0%	57.1%	50.0%	57.1%	0.0%	0.0%
Phd(n=7)	100.0%	100.0%	0.0%	14.3%	0.0%	85.7%	42.9%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Total (n=112) mean	82.7%	58.2%	12.7%	1.8%	4.5%	47.7%	51.4%	90.1%	0.9%	7.2%

*Less Risk of Physical communication
 **Need to Special Devices
 ***Less Communication with Teachers

Table 4. Desire of future classes even after COVID19 pandemic according to students' opinion

Grade	Type of Classes		
	Online	Physical	Mix
BSC(n=91)	13.3%	42.2%	44.4%
Msc(n=14)	7.1%	7.1%	85.7%
Phd(n=7)	57.1%	0.0%	42.9%
Total (n=112) mean	15.3%	35.1%	49.5%

Figure 1. The device used to attend an online class

Online classes in the context of heart pathophysiology were structured as follows: 59.8% of the course materials were pre-recorded, and 40.2% were presented live. Notably, 92.9% of students utilized Adobe Connect as the platform for attending these online classes. Additionally, the use of PowerPoint slides was a prevalent method for delivering lessons in this field, with 88.4% of instructors utilizing them (Figure 2). Among undergraduate students, a significant 78.8% reported that their professors made use of PowerPoint presentations for teaching. However, in the case of online classes for postgraduate students, 24.3% of the instructors relied on reference books for their presentations. This figure was slightly lower at 10.8% for PhD students.

Figure 2. Presentation methods in online classes

61.6% of students have attended more than 80% of online classes, and 93.8% admitted experiencing issues during online classes. All undergraduate students have attended more than 80% of their online classes.

Insufficient access to online platforms has been identified as a significant factor contributing to students' absenteeism (64.3 percent) (Figure 3). 93.8 percent of undergraduate students mentioned inadequate internet access as a contributing factor to their lack of attendance or absenteeism in online programs. 21.1 percent of postgraduate students reported that the timing of classes was inconvenient. 26.3 percent of PhD students cited the same reason for non-attendance in certain online courses.

Figure 3. The reason for the absence of students in online classes

In the context of cardiac pathophysiology, it is essential to understand the various methods of communication between students and professors during live classes. According to the data presented in Figure 4, it is evident that students primarily relied on messaging through the online platform to interact with their professors. Among undergraduate students, 86.5% reported using this method to communicate with their professors. Additionally, 38.5% of postgraduate students utilized telephone

communication, whereas 53.8% of PhD students also preferred this method to connect with their professors. This reliance on digital communication channels underscores the importance of effective online communication in the field of cardiac pathophysiology education.

Figure 4. How students communicate with professors during virtual classes

The students reported their communication with professors during recorded classes, and the methods they used varied. A total of 85.1% of undergraduate students in the recorded classes have communicated with professors via the Navid system, a platform commonly used for online courses. On the other hand, 25.9% of postgraduate students have communicated with professors through class groups on social networks, while 37.5% of PhD students have preferred telephone calls for this purpose. When students were asked about professor-student communication in the context of heart pathophysiology, 48.2 percent responded that it was on an average basis. Specifically, 94.4% of undergraduate students assessed their professors' communication as moderate, suggesting that it met their expectations. In contrast, 33.3% of graduate students rated their professors' communication as excellent, indicating a higher level of satisfaction with the communication quality. Among PhD students, 50% expressed a similar sentiment, perceiving their professors' communication as excellent as well. This reflects the varying opinions and experiences of students regarding the quality of communication in the study of heart pathophysiology.

Figure 5. The advantage of distance education from the perspective

The most significant benefit of virtual education, according to students, was the reduced interaction with others during the Covid-19 pandemic (81.3%) (Figure 5). Among undergraduate students, 79.1% mentioned the advantage of online classes being limited contact with others during the pandemic. In contrast, postgraduate students highlighted decreased absenteeism compared to face-to-face classes (38.5%), and 10.9% of PhD students emphasized the reduced cost and time spent on transportation as a positive aspect of this class format.

Furthermore, the primary drawback of this educational approach was the inadequate clinical learning experience (89.3%) (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Disadvantages of virtual classes from the students' point of view

Students identified the following factors influencing the pathophysiology of the heart: improvements in mechanisms regulating cardiac function (7.1 percent), the role of professor-led instruction (73.2 percent), alterations in cardiac rhythm (25.9 percent), and increased student involvement in cardiac issues (10.7 percent). 86.6 percent of undergraduate students have implemented changes to enhance the efficacy of cardiac pathophysiology education. However, 25% of postgraduate students reported changes in cardiac rhythm, and 13.8% of PhD students mentioned improved professor-led instruction to enhance the understanding of heart pathophysiology. Undergraduate students expressed a satisfaction rate ranging from 60% to 90% regarding their understanding of heart pathophysiology. The satisfaction level for 85.7% of postgraduate students exceeded 90%, while 16.2% of PhD students fell within the 60-90% satisfaction range. Overall, students' satisfaction with learning about heart pathophysiology was generally positive (35.7%). 44.6% of students participated in educational sessions on heart pathophysiology, and their satisfaction with these online sessions was rated at 77.7%. Additionally, in other research, such as a study conducted by Mishra et al. in India, 77.5% of ophthalmology students found participation in online sessions beneficial¹⁶. The students also expressed their post-pandemic preferences, with 34.8% opting for virtual classes, 15.2% choosing in-person classes, and 49.1% selecting a combination of both. Furthermore, 50.9% indicated their desire to continue online classes even after the Covid-19 pandemic.

Discussion

As COVID-19 emerged as a pandemic and led to global lockdowns, many academic institutions transitioned to online learning as a safety measure for both professors and students^{20,21}. This study aims to examine the experiences of students in Optometry across three different academic levels during their engagement in distance e-learning, which is a relatively recent approach adopted by Iranian universities in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, distance e-learning emerged as a novel method for sustaining educational continuity. Our investigation focused on understanding the challenges faced by students during their adoption of this new learning approach, limitations encountered, the performance of online platforms, overall satisfaction, and future prospects in the field of cardiac pathophysiology.

The results of this study indicate that online education, from the perspective of optometry students, aligns with the findings of numerous other studies. These results demonstrate that satisfaction with online classes increases as students' progress through their academic levels. Undergraduate students displayed a satisfaction rate of 60-90%, while PhD students exhibited satisfaction rates exceeding 90%. This pattern is consistent with research conducted by Jonuscheit et al.²², Hajizadeh et al.²³, Sehgal et al.²⁴, Mishra et al.²⁵, and Radha et al.²⁶ The accessibility of smartphones and personal computers has significantly facilitated the performance of undergraduate students in online classrooms. This trend is similar to findings in Libya, as reported by AlSoufi et al.²⁷, where students utilized smartphones to attend online classes. It is noteworthy that a majority of students had not previously experienced online classes.

In the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, the duration of online classes exceeded 30 days. This is in contrast to a study conducted among medical students in Jordan, where the duration was approximately two weeks. Most classes were conducted between 8-14, with the primary platform being "Adobe Connect." In Jordan, medical students often used the Zoom software. Similarly, Abbasi et al.²⁸ reported that Zoom was the most widely used platform during this period. A study by Rajhan et al.²¹ in India and among optometry professors highlighted video conferences as the most common teaching method.

Drawbacks of online classrooms included insufficient class time and poor internet connectivity. In the Jordan study, students cited poor internet access and inappropriate class timing as reasons for missing online classes. In AlSoufi et al.'s study in 2020²⁷, students cited financial difficulties as a major hindrance to attending online classes. Moreover, Al-balas' 2020 study⁵ revealed that

poor instruction and inadequate internet access were the most significant disadvantages of online classes. In a simultaneous study across multiple countries conducted by Abbasi et al.²⁸, poor internet access was identified as the primary factor impeding online learning.

Benefits of online classes included financial savings and reduced physical interaction during the COVID-19 epidemic. Deming et al.²⁹ observed in 2015 that online programs are more cost-effective than traditional classroom instruction. According to a 2020 survey by Sindiani et al.¹⁰, students identified the primary advantage of online classrooms as maintaining social distance and having less contact with others. Consequently, Al-balas' 2020⁵ study highlighted time-saving as the most significant advantage of conducting online classes. Communication with professors varied depending on the students' academic level. PhD students primarily communicated with their professors through telephone, while undergraduate students used the Navid platform to send messages. According to the results of this study, the majority of students at all academic levels expressed satisfaction levels exceeding 60% with online classes, with higher academic levels demonstrating increased satisfaction.

To enhance the effectiveness of online classrooms and student satisfaction, it is recommended that educational programs consider incorporating online classes as a complementary method alongside traditional, face-to-face instruction, even after the COVID-19 pandemic. About 50% of students expressed a desire to continue using online classes post-pandemic. This aligns with the findings of Abbasi et al.'s multi-country study²⁸, where students indicated their preference for a combination of face-to-face and online classes after the COVID-19 epidemic concludes. In conclusion, this study only assessed the personal views of students, and further research is needed to evaluate the practical outcomes of online education. Additionally, it is imperative to gather the perspectives of optometry professors and university staff regarding this novel educational approach, particularly in the context of cardiac pathophysiology.

Conclusions

The Covid-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on various aspects of human life. It has also led to significant transformations in optometry education, and these changes are expected to leave a lasting impact even beyond the pandemic. Thankfully, students generally found the transition to online education to be satisfactory. One of the primary reasons for this positive response is the prioritization of health and effective time management. However, there are certain drawbacks to this educational shift, such as issues related to poor internet connectivity and reduced interaction with professors. It appears that, post-pandemic, students are inclined to maintain a hybrid approach to learning, combining online classes with traditional face-to-face instruction. The Covid-19 pandemic has undeniably accelerated the adoption of online learning methodologies on a global scale. Nevertheless, these methods do not appear to be entirely effective in enhancing students' clinical and practical skills. As a result, the integration of both online and in-person teaching methods in the education of students becomes imperative. The introduction of new educational platforms may help address some of the challenges, with a particular emphasis on improving clinical and practical education.

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References

1. Wang C, Horby PW, Hayden FG, Gao GF. A novel coronavirus outbreak of global health concern. *The lancet* 2020;395(10223):470-473.
2. Xia J, Tong J, Liu M, Shen Y, Guo D. Evaluation of coronavirus in tears and conjunctival secretions of patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection. *J Med Virol* 2020;92(6):589-594.
3. Ayatollahi A, Kangari H, Shahcheraghi SH, Abdi S, Mirfendereski SA. COVID-19; A Review for Eye Care Practitioners. *Ann Rom Soc Cell Biol* 2021;25(6):3750-3760.
4. Schneider SL, Council ML. Distance learning in the era of COVID-19. *Arch Dermatol Res* 2021;313(5):389-390.
5. Al-Balas M, Al-Balas HI, Jaber HM, Obeidat K, Al-Balas H, Abo-rajoo EA. Distance learning in clinical medical education amid

- COVID-19 pandemic in Jordan: current situation, challenges, and perspectives. *BMC Med Educ* 2020;20(1):341.
6. Ayatollahi J, Ayatollahi F, Ayatollahi R, Shahcheraghi SH. Computer and internet use among undergraduate medical students in Iran. *Pak J Med Sci* 2014;30(5):1054.
 7. Seymour-Walsh AE, Bell A, Weber A, Smith T. Adapting to a new reality: COVID-19 coronavirus and online education in the health professions. *Rural Remote Health* 2020;20(2):6000.
 8. Ortiz PA. Teaching in the time of COVID-19. *Biochem Mol Biol Educ* 2020;48(3):201.
 9. Iancu AM, Kemp MT, Alam HB. Unmuting Medical Students' Education: Utilizing Telemedicine During the COVID-19 Pandemic and Beyond. *J Med Internet Res* 2020;22(7):e19667.
 10. Sindiani AM, Obeidat N, Alshdaifat E, Elsalem L, Alwani MM, Rashwashdeh H, et al. Distance education during the COVID-19 outbreak: A cross-sectional study among medical students in North of Jordan. *Ann Med Surg* 2020;59:186-194.
 11. Townsend MJ. Learning to nurse during the pandemic: a student's reflections. *Br J Nurs* 2020;29(16):972-973.
 12. Zuo L, Dillman D, Miller Juvé A. Learning at home during COVID-19: A multi-institutional virtual learning collaboration. *Med Educ* 2020;54(7):664-665.
 13. Diaz MCG, Walsh BM. Telesimulation-based education during COVID-19. *Clin Teach* 2021;18(2):121-125.
 14. Song P, Walline J. Virtual Technologies of Care in a Time of Viral Crisis: An Ethnographic View from Hong Kong. *Somatosphere*; 2020.
 15. Bambakidis NC, Tomei KL. Impact of COVID-19 on neurosurgery resident training and education. *J Neurosurg* 2020;133(1):10-11.
 16. Mishra K, Boland MV, Woreta FA. Incorporating a virtual curriculum into ophthalmology education in the coronavirus disease-2019 era. *Curr Opin Ophthalmol* 2020;31(5):380-385.
 17. Liaw ST, Gray K. Clinical Health Informatics Education for a 21st Century World. *Health Informatics: IOS Press*; 2010; 479-491.
 18. Einarson E, Moen A, Kolberg R, Flingtorp G, Linnerud E. Interactive eLearning-a safe place to practice. *Stud Health Technol Inform* 2009;146:841-850.
 19. Casimiro L, MacDonald CJ, Thompson TL, Stodel EJ. Grounding theories of W (e) Learn: A framework for online interprofessional education. *J Interprof Care* 2009;23(4):390-400.
 20. Gerkin KL, Taylor TH, Weatherby FM. The perception of learning and satisfaction of nurses in the online environment. *J Nurses Prof Dev* 2009;25(1):E8-E13.
 21. Rajhans V, Memon U, Patil V, Goyal A. Impact of COVID-19 on academic activities and way forward in Indian Optometry. *J Optom* 2020;13(4):216-226.
 22. Jonuscheit S, Lam AKC, Schmid KL, Flanagan J, Martin R, Troilo D. COVID-19: ensuring safe clinical teaching at university optometry schools. *Ophthalmic Physiol Opt* 2021;41(1):144-156.
 23. Hajizadeh R, Papisad M. Effectiveness of Massage after Impulse Exercises on Pain and Proprioception Sense of Ankle in Female Beginner Taekwondo. *Anesth Pain* 2019;10(3):71-80.
 24. Sehgal S, Shinde L, Madheswaran G, Mukherjee P, Verkicharla P, Easwaran S. Impact of COVID-19 on Indian optometrists: A student, educator, and practitioner's perspective. *Indian J Ophthalmol* 2021;69(4):958-963.
 25. Mishra D, Nair AG, Gandhi RA, Gogate PJ, Mathur S, Bhushan P, et al. The impact of COVID-19 related lockdown on ophthalmology training programs in India - Outcomes of a survey. *Indian J Ophthalmol* 2020;68(6):999-1004.
 26. Radha R, Mahalakshmi K, Kumar VS, Saravanakumar A. E-Learning during lockdown of Covid-19 pandemic: A global perspective. *Int J Control Autom* 2020;13(4):1088-1099.
 27. Alsoufi A, Alsuyhili A, Msherghi A, Elhadi A, Atiyah H, Ashini A. Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on medical education: Medical students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding electronic learning. *PLoS One* 2020;15(11):e0242905.
 28. Abbasi MS, Ahmed N, Sajjad B, Alshahrani A, Saeed S, Sarfaraz S, et al. E-Learning perception and satisfaction among health sciences students amid the COVID-19 pandemic. *Work* 2020;67(3):549-556.
 29. Deming DJ, Goldin C, Katz LF, Yuchtman N. Can online learning bend the higher education cost curve. *Am Econ Rev* 2015;105(5):496-501.